

**UNIVERSITY OF CAPE COAST
COLLEGE OF HEALTH AND ALLIED SCIENCES
DEPARTMENT OF BIOMEDICAL SCIENCE**

**KNOWLEDGE OF THE BENEFITS OF IODIZED SALT AND
RISK ASSOCIATED WITH CONSUMPTION OF SALTY FOODS
AMONG UCC STUDENT**

BY

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DECLARATION

I, Eshun Gregory, hereby declare that except for references to other people's work which have been duly acknowledged, this thesis is the result of my own research carried out at the University of Cape Coast under the supervision of Dr. Adladza Kofi Amegah. This thesis contains no material previously published by another person in the university or elsewhere.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction Low intake of iodine is the main cause of iodine deficiency disorders (IDDs) such as goitre and cretinism. Universal salt iodization as well as policies regulating intake of iodized salt are the main preventive measure to control iodine deficiency. Iodine Deficiency Disorders are endemic in inland and mountainous area. This study therefore explored the knowledge of students in UCC on the awareness and use of iodized salt as well as the effectiveness of the policies and laws on the use of iodized salt. Also, this study assessed awareness of students on risk associated with consumption of salt.

Methodology- The study was conducted in University of Cape Coast, one of the public universities in Ghana using a cross-sectional design. Three hundred (300) students were sampled for study. A standardized questionnaire was used to collect relevant data. Descriptive and inferential statistical analysis was undertaken.

Results: The study revealed that knowledge on iodized salt was quite high with 93% of the students using iodized salt. There was an association between educational level and knowledge of iodized salt ($X^2=11.54$, $p=0.021$). The proportion of students who knew the benefits of iodized salt was 72%. A high proportion (93%) of the students did not know about the policy regulating intake of iodized salt. The students consume salt mostly from dried salted fish. Less than half (42%) of the respondents knew that salt causes health problems with hypertension being the main salt-related health problem mentioned.

Conclusion: Knowledge on benefits of iodized salt was very high among students. However, majority of students were unaware of the health problems associated with high salt intake.

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DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to the Almighty God for making everything possible for my entire family, friends and myself. May God bless anyone who supported me especially Mr. and Mrs. Eshun who believed in me even when I did not believe in myself. Thank you.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
Declaration	ii
Abstract	iii-iv
Acknowledgement	v
Dedication	vi
Table of Content	vii-viii
List of Tables	ix
List of Abbreviations	x
Chapter One	1-7
Introduction	
Problem Statement	
Justification	
Objectives	
Hypothesis	
Chapter Two	8-19
Literature Review	
Knowledge and Awareness of the Use of Iodized Salt	
Awareness of Salt Intake Recommendations	
Knowledge of the Salt Content of Commonly Consumed Foods	
Knowledge on Salty Diet Related Disease	
Legislation Governing the Use of Iodized Salt and Salted Foods	
Factors Associated with Consumption of Iodized Salt and Salted Foods	

Chapter Three	20-21
Study Design	
Study Population and Sample Procedure	
Data Analysis	
Research Instruments	
Chapter Four	22-28
Result	
Respondents Demographics (Table 2)	
Respondents Knowledge and Awareness of Iodized Salt (Table 3)	
Respondents Knowledge, Consumption and Risk of Salt Ingredients (Table 4)	
Chi-Square Association between Demographic and Heard About Iodized Salt and Salt	
Chapter Five	29-32
Discussion	
Synthesis with the previous studies	
Conclusion and Recommendations	
Appendix	33-43
References	
Questionnaires*	

LISTS OF TABLES

Table 2.0 Studies assessing knowledge about salt intake and recommendations.

Table 4.1: Respondents Knowledge and Awareness of Iodized Salt

Table 4.2: Respondents Knowledge, Consumption and Risk of Salt Ingredients

Table 4.3: Chi-Square Association between Demographic Characteristics, Ever Heard of Iodized Salt and Salt Usage.

LISTS OF ABBREVIATIONS

DHS - Demographic and Health Survey

FDB - Food and Drug Board

GHS - Ghana Health Service

GSS - Ghana Statistical Service

ICCIDD- International Council for the Control of Iodine Deficiency Disorders

IEC - Information, Education and Communication

INF - International Network Forum

IQ - Intelligent Quotient

IDA - Iron Deficiency Anemia

IDD - Iodine Deficiency Disorder

K103 - potassium Iodide

MICS - Multiple Indicator Cluster Survey

MOE Ministry of Education

MOH Ministry of Health

T3 Tri-iodothyrosine

T4 Thyroxine

Ug/L - Microgram/Litre

UNICEF- United Nation International Child and Education Fund

USI - Universal Salt Iodization

WHA - World Health Assembly

WHO - World Health Organization

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 BACKGROUND

Non-communicable diseases and communicable diseases have been the major health issue globally but the developed countries face more non-communicable diseases while developing countries have been loaded with both diseases (Lopez et al., 2006). With emphasis on non-communicable diseases, salt has been the direct and indirect inevitable causality of some non-communicable diseases (Brown et al., 2009). WHO, 2004 and Zimmerman et al., 2008, stated in their studies with sufficient evidence that micronutrient malnutrition has been an adverse public health problem globally and reported to be on the rise in developing countries. Shekar et al., 2007 and Black et al., 2008 reported major micronutrient deficiencies of public health concern to be zinc, iron, vitamin A and Iodine.

Globally, people who are at-risk live in iodine deficient areas amount to more than one billion and therefore have the potential of developing Iodine deficiency disorder (Melse-Boonstra et al., 1998). An international renowned agency such as WHO, UNICEF and ICCIDD have therefore supported it as a serious public health problem and had collaborated in efforts to manage and prevent IDD. Iodine deficiency has been regarded as irreversible but preventable deficiency with effect on embryo and foetus development during pregnancy (Zimmerman et al., 2008; Hetzel, 2007; WHO, 2000). IDD effects on foetus include stillbirth, abortion, miscarriage in pregnancy, brain damage and congenital abnormalities. In severe cases, iodine deficiency may cause cretinism and mental retardation with impaired physical development in school children and also in adults, goiter is highly traceable to iodine deficiency (Hetzel and Pandav, 1994). However, a whole variety of naturally occurring goitrogenic agents

has been identified as significant potential of causing IDD (Gaitan, 1980). Zimmerman, 2007 in assessment study of iodine nutritional status conducted among school children concluded that one third of school children remain iodine deficient but it has been generally stated by WHO, ICCIDD and UNICEF, 2001, that people living in iodine deficient areas may have intelligence quotients of equal to or less than 13.5 which is much lower than people living in iodine sufficient areas (Bleichrodt and Born 1994). Therefore, iodine deficiency has significant association with deficit in cognitive functions (INF, 2010). In Ghana, a study carried out by Asibey-Berko and Orraca-Tetteh, 1995 was conducted on school children, adolescents and women of child-bearing to assess the nation-wide distribution and magnitude of IDD and the result showed that prevalence of total goitre was 20% in the randomly selected 27 districts surveyed with more goitre cases in the northern and western region of Ghana. In a similar study in 21 districts, it was found out that only two districts had optimal iodine concentration and consumption while the rest range from severe to mild iodine deficiency (Asibey-Berko and Orraca Tetteh 1995, WHO, ICCIDD and UNICEF, 2001). Most recent study in 2014 by Ghana Demographic Health Survey had stated that knowledge of the iodized salt was 8 in 10 women aged 15-45 but rural had less knowledge about iodized salt than urban (Ghana Demographic Health Survey, 2014).

Food fortification, especially fortification of salt with iodine has been the worldwide proven strategy and most preferred effective technology recommended for eliminating IDD and its associated disorder. Salt has been the most optimal vehicle for iodization due to the fact that it has been used by all age group regardless of the socio-economic status of individual. Salt is the dietary ingredient consumed irregularly in same amount universally (WHO, UNICEF and ICCIDD, 2007; Mannar

and Dunn, 1995). Adequately iodized salt having about 20 to 40 parts per million of iodine for human consumption has been recommended by International Council for Control of Iodine deficiency diseases (WHO, UNICEF and ICCIDD, 2007). Globally, there has been sufficient improvement but less satisfaction in consumption of iodized salt of about 70% household consumption from 1990 to date which is below global target goal of about 90% household (Dalmiya et al. 2004). In a study carried out at University of Ghana using iodized salt made up of 20ppm iodine to prepare 10 Ghanaian foods led to loss of iodine in food while for the preparation of the similar food with 40ppm iodized salt, only few prepared foods had enough iodine left to meet the adult recommended daily intake of 150mg. Ghana Standard Board had therefore recommended 50ppm salt iodization in Ghana in order to gain enough iodine left to satisfy health needs (GHS and UNICEF, 2009). Legal backup to the Universal Salt Iodization in Ghana of the Food and Drugs Amendment Act 523 was set in 1996 and became effective in 1997 stating that any salt to be consumed by humans and animals should be iodized (Agble and Armah, 1999). This intervention therefore seeks to target iodized salt consumption as priority health strategy through careful monitoring and availability of iodized salt in the market by Minister of Health.

Salt as a vehicle for fortification could also be associated with raised blood pressure (BP) and adverse cardiovascular health (Conlin, 2007). An epidemiological study had proved the negative effect of salt intake on BP among individual and had concluded that salt reduction strategies could be beneficial to hypertension management of which African descendants respond well than the westerners (Sacks et al., 2001.). Salt induced cardiovascular diseases (CVD) and hypertension had been accounting for 17.3 million deaths each year globally and this figure was expected to

increase to 23.6 million by the year 2030, if possible, measure are not taken (Mendis et al., 2011). In developed countries, the majority of salt consumed had been incorporated in processed foods while in developing countries like Ghana, consumption of dried salty foods and addition of salt to already prepared food at the table has been the major source of salt intake (Mattes and Donnelly, 1991).

In a study conducted in 2014 to determine the relationship between reduction in salt intake and blood pressure as well as other cardiovascular diseases it was found that reduction in salt intake is the key factor to the fall of Blood pressure from 2003 to 2011 (MacGregor et al, 2014). Ghana Demographic Health Survey, 2014) had reported that about 84% of total women surveyed has been using salty foods from different sources with variations in percentages for the specific salty foods they consume as well as geographical variation in salty food consumption among urban, rural and regional localities. A review of twenty-two studies on salt knowledge and salt-related practice in general population indicated that individuals knew about the health risk of salt but had no knowledge about daily recommended intake and highly salted food products were unknowingly taken (Sarmugram and Worsley 2014). Also, four studies had concluded significant association of relationship between salt knowledge and salt-related dietary practice (Sarmugram and Worsley, 2014).

Therefore, this study aims at assessing the level of awareness of a student concerning the benefits and utilization of iodized salt, and knowledge of the risk associated with salty food.

1.1 PROBLEM STATEMENT

Globally, more than one billion people are at risk of developing Iodine Deficiency Diseases (Melse-Boonstra et al., 1998) while 17.3 billion account for mortality of high blood pressure and cardiovascular diseases (Mendis et al., 2011). WHO had

given a proven strategy to address this public health through 90% target of Universal Salt Iodization program and salt reduction strategies as well as enactment of policy and law to ensure its enforcement of this program in all developed and developing countries facing IDD problem (WHO, UNICEF and ICCIDD, 2007).

Ghana Demographic and Health Survey, 2014 had reported that an average of 86% of women aged 15-49 had heard of iodized salt while 84% had been consuming any salted foods. This was below the global and national target of 90% which was to have been attained by the end of 2005 and sustained by 2011 (Ahiadeka et al., 2012). Other key findings indicated that 63% of women and 86% of men were not aware that they had high blood pressure (GSS, 2015). Universal Salt Iodization has been in existence in Ghana since 1995 yet a significant portion of Ghanaian population does not consume iodized salt despite government efforts and salt industry efforts (Agble and Armah, 1999). An assessment had portrayed very low consumption rate of iodized salt. The assessment had also found that low level of awareness on iodized salt, and complaints from consumers about unavailability and high cost of iodized salt were the key factors of these results (Buxton and Bagueune, 2012).

IDD and salt induced health problems have still been in existence due to lack of proper Information, Education and Communication (I.E.C.) through the mass media like radio, television as well as lack of proper guideline for monitoring the consumption of hidden salted foods, availability and accessibility of iodized salt (UNICEF and MOH, 1997). This study therefore intends to assess the level of knowledge of the benefits of iodized salt and consumption rate of salty ingredients and the effectiveness of policies on its usage.

1.2 JUSTIFICATION

The Global and national target of 90% consumption of iodized salt by individual has not been achieved by Ghana despite Ghana being the leading producer of salt in the sub-region (Ahiadeka et al., 2012)). Despite the many benefits of iodized salt, there are numerous reports of low utilization of iodized salt among individual leading to high prevalence of iodine deficiency diseases especially among school aged individual. A gradual and sustained reduction in the amount of salt added to food by the food industry during food processing and cooking by individual are an effective way in controlling high blood pressure in which Sub-Sahara Africans respond rapidly well yet high blood pressure and cardiovascular diseases are inevitable OPD cases (Sacks et al., 2001). Again, most common non-communicable diseases like iodine deficiency disorder, high blood pressure and cardiovascular diseases have still been in existence due to lack of attention and educative information on it basic cause that is salt which has always been hidden in our daily foods resulting in high cases of high blood pressure. This has therefore brought an interest to public health sector and thus study has placed all the necessary measures to identify, manage and control these rising non-communicable diseases as well as to provide and investigate information on the inability of Ghana to reach the global and national target as at now even with enacted policy and law on iodization and reduction of salt among University of Cape Coast students.

1.3 MAIN OBJECTIVE

The main objectives of the study were to assess the awareness and knowledge of university students on iodized salt benefits, and health risk associated with salted food intake.

1.4 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVE

- To determine the level of consumption of iodized salt among students.
- To assess the effects of demographic and other factors on the consumption of iodized salt among students.
- To assess the awareness of policies and laws regulating the use of iodized salt among students
- To ascertain the salty food mostly consumed by students
- To assess students' knowledge about the risk associated with consumption of salted foods among UCC students.

1.6 HYPOTHESIS

- Knowledge of the benefits of iodized salt consumption among UCC students is high.
- Awareness of the health problems associated with consumption of salted food among UCC students is low.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 INTRODUCTION

43rd World Health Assembly (WHA) of WHO in 1990 had objective goal to eliminate IDD as public health problem by the year 2000. The self-assurance was the possibility of elimination of IDD in developed country through simple cost-effective process of salt iodization and consumption (Hetzel et al., 1996). The countries involved were United States of America (USA), United Kingdom (UK), Switzerland, Australia and many others (Hetzel et al., 1996). The ultimate goal of elimination could be possible through sustained advocacy, resource mobilization, monitoring and evaluation (Kavishe, 1997). The member countries of 52nd WHA were encouraged to evaluate the iodine status of their population and the quality of iodized salt involving the goal of sustainable elimination of IDD as public health problem (WHA, 1999).

Some studies indicated the need for sustained governmental, industrial and popular support for programme to eliminate IDD to prevent self-satisfaction even after controllable state (Zhou et al., 1997).

There has been enough evidence that high salt intake increases the risk of hypertension and cardiovascular diseases. This paper therefore reviews the current level of salt knowledge and dietary salt intake practice in the world with emphasis on Ghanaian population. Some studies showed that knowledge of recommended daily intake and understanding of relationship between salt and health were very poor thus there is significant association of salt knowledge and salt-related dietary practice that were well established (Sarmugum and Worsely, 2014).

2.1 KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS OF THE USE OF IODIZED SALT

Wheeler and Van der Haar (2004) proved that household wealth was significant determinant of the use of iodized salt than educational level in their study conducted in Mali, Zambia, Uganda, Rwanda and Turkmenistan. On contrary, Ahiadeke et al., 2012 reported that the significant contributing factors in determining household utilization of adequately iodized salt were access to information (media), educational level of household heads and income status of households. The study revealed household with low educational background used iodized salt less (Ahiadeke et al., 2012).

Research by (Adjei, 2002), the study addressed the determinant of iodized salt consumption in household in Kintampo sub-district in Ghana. Sex of the household, household size and knowledge on some common IDD were the key factors considered.

There is association of income levels as in richer and poorer household with iodized salt consumption in multiple indicator cluster survey (2010-2011) in five highly densely populated communities in Accra namely Nima, James Town, Accra New Town, Bubuashie and La. The iodized salt usage in the richer households were 80% while that of poorer household usage were 53%. The further findings state that households using salt that were not iodized were 24% meanwhile 13% household used inadequately iodized salt that less than 15ppm.

Tepas et al, 2010, found that 81.3% of household with knowledge on IDD consumed a significant higher proportion of adequately iodized salt than the 68.7% household without knowledge on IDD (Tepas et al., 2010). Ghana Health Service, 2003 survey conducted in Tema Municipality found that 300 sample salt tested had only 63% iodized. Also, high cost, unavailability, not important, used to local salt and never

heard about it were reasons given by the household heads Health Service (2003). Yamada et al., 1998, reported that the price of iodized salt is slightly higher than that of common salt. UNICEF, 2008 strengthened Yamada's report that cost of iodized salt is one of the factors accounting for low iodized salt intake.

Buxton and Bagueune, 2012, reported that unavailability of iodized salt in the market had caused 8.6% household to use common salt exclusively in a survey conducted in Bia district of Western Region of Ghana.

2.2 AWARENESS OF SALT INTAKE RECOMMENDATIONS

Fifteen studies had examined participants' awareness of salt intake recommendations with regardless of the differences in education levels and the countries where the studies were conducted. Some of the participants (at least 70%) in the 13 studies never knew or recall the recommended amount of salt intake (Kim et al., 2012). Charlton et al., 2010; Claro et al., 2012; Grimes et al., 2009 and International Food Information Council, 2011 were the only four studies that with less than 10% participants who were able to identify the recommended amount of salt intake.

2.3 KNOWLEDGE OF THE SALT CONTENT OF COMMONLY CONSUMED FOODS

Studies that examined the perceived salt content of foods reported that more than 50% of the respondents were able to identify high salt items such as bacon and chips. Seven out of nine studies which examined whether respondents were aware that processed foods are the main sources of salt in their diet indicated that more than 70% of the respondents were aware that processed foods are their main source of salt (Sarmugum and Worsely 2014). However, two large-scale surveys, Consensus Action on Salt and Health, 2010 and International Food Information Council, 2011

conducted in the UK and the USA reported that fewer than 15% of the participants could correctly identify bread and cereals as the major contributors of salt to British and American diets.

2.4 CONSEQUENCES OF HIGH SALT INTAKE

All studies on salty induced diseases found that at least 80% of the participants were aware of the relationships between high salt intake and hypertension Health (Canada, 2009). However, awareness of other cardiovascular diseases such as stroke, heart diseases or heart attacks were not well known (though in the majority of studies awareness was above 60%). Nearly half of the participants were able to correctly identify the relationships between high salt intakes (Marakis et al., 2014).

Table 2.0 Studies Assessing Knowledge about Salt Intake and Recommendation.

Author (Year)	Dietary Salt Recommendation (% Correct)	Food Sources of Salt in the Diet/Salt Content of Foods	Diet-Disease Relationships (% Correct)
Charlton et al., (2010)	5%	88% identified processed foods such as breads, breakfast cereals, tinned foods and takeaway foods as the major sources of salt in the diet. >80% identified salt content in foods such as bacon pizza and vegemite as high. More than 70% were able to identify salt content in fresh foods such as carrot, cooked rice and full cream milk as low. Only 26% correctly identified salt content in cornflakes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Salt worsens health: 62% ● Hypertension: 97% ● Heart attack: 88% ● Stroke: 72%

Author (Year)	Dietary Salt Recommendation (% Correct)	Food Sources of Salt in the Diet/Salt Content of Foods	Diet-Disease Relationships (% Correct)
Claro et al., (2012)	7%; No detailed information for countries were provided	Not applicable	Eating a diet high in salt can cause serious health issues (% agree) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Total: 88.5%; Argentina: 97.5%; Canada: 93.2%; Chile: 89%; Costa Rica: 86.9%; Ecuador: 75.6%
Consensus Action on Salt and Health (2003)	75% (Policy Makers (MP) and health professionals (HP)).43% general consumers (GC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main source of salt is in processed foods: 100% (MP), 89% (HP). • 61% were unaware of salt content hidden in foods like cornflakes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hypertension: 98% (MP), 100% (HI), 97% (GC).Stroke: 67% (MP), 58% (HI), 51% (GC).Kidney disease: 42% (MP), 21% (HI), 18% (GC). Osteoporosis: 11% (total participants).

Author (Year)	Dietary Salt Recommen dation (%Correct)	Food Sources of Salt in the Diet/Salt Content of Foods	Diet-Disease Relationships (% Correct)
Health Canada (2009)	75% of respondents provided estimates that are within the range of adequate daily intake (0–1500 mg).	72% believed processed foods are the single largest source of salt in Canadian diet. Others believed the following were the sources of where most salt in Canadian diet comes from: Salt added during cooking (4%), salt added at the table (9%), restaurant foods (13%). The majority identified the following foods as high in salt: processed meats (90%), canned soups (77%), pickled foods (74%) and frozen dinners (74%) and the following foods as low in salt: fresh meat or fish (70%), fresh vegetables (90%), whole wheat breads (48%) and the following as foods with moderate amount of salt: cheese (47%), canned tuna (42%).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 92% agree around 80 per cent of salt in the average Canadians' diet comes from processed food. Hypertension: 96% Stroke: 85% Heart disease: 92% Osteoporosis: 54%
Grimes et al., (2009)	5%	Not applicable	Hypertension:>88% Stroke: about 60% Kidney disease: about 50%, Osteoporosis: about 10%

Author (Year)	Dietary Salt Recommendation (%Correct)	Food Sources of Salt in the Diet/Salt Content of Foods	Diet-Disease Relationships (% Correct)
Kim et al., (2012)	Not applicable	<p>More than 90% correctly identified 7 out of 8 items low in salt (apples, fresh green beans, cookies, chocolate, Jello-O, yoghurt and steamed fish) correctly as low in salt.</p> <p>More than 70% correctly identified 11 out of 15 items as high in salt (examples: potato chips, ham, pickles); 3 high salt items least identified as high salt were processed cheese, cottage cheese and cheddar cheese. Participants were also unlikely to think of these foods as salty.</p>	<p>Hypertension: 96.1/97.1%</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Heart disease: 12.3/9.8% ● High cholesterol: 39.1/30.7% ● Stroke: 82.2/86.3% ● Kidney disease: 67.9/68.5% ● Bone health: 30.9/36.6%
Marakis et al., (2014)	11.10%	Main source of salt in diet: salt in cooking (38%), bread (3%), meat and sausages (20%).	<p>Diet high in salt could cause serious health problems (95%)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Hypertension: 69%, Kidney stones: 59% Osteoporosis: 31%
Marshall et al., (2007)	28%	67% agreed with the statement “65%–70% of salt intake comes from processed foods”.	89% agreed eating salt raises blood pressure, 25% agreed salt plays a part in osteoporosis.

Author (Year)	Dietary Salt Recommendation (%Correct)	Food Sources of Salt in the Diet/Salt Content of Foods	Diet-Disease Relationships (% Correct)
Wyllie et al., (2011)	25%	Main source of salt in diet: salt in processed foods such as breads, breakfast cereals, tinned foods and takeaways (77%)	Hypertension: 83% , Heart attack: 85%, Stroke: 72% Kidney disease: 58% Osteoporosis: 18%
Zhang et al., (2013)	29.3% (urban sample), 19.2% (rural sample)	Not applicable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Hypertension: 60.3% (urban) ● Hypertension: 49.0% (rural)
Webster et al., (2010)	14%	Processed foods are main sources of salt in the diet: about 75%. On average, participants were able to correctly classify 10 common foods as high, medium or low in salt content two thirds of the time	Salt worsens health: 67%. Hypertension: 87%, Stroke: 77% Heart attack: 75% kidney disease: 44%
Consensus Action on Salt and Health (2010)	Not applicable	The foods most commonly mentioned as the foods that contribute most salt to the UK diet (from a list of 10 foods) were crisps and snacks (73%), ready meals (65%) and meat products (36%). However, only meat products were actually in the top three. Only 13% mentioned bread, and 12% mentioned breakfast cereal.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 92% were aware that salt can damage their health ● Hypertension: 69% ● Stroke: 34% ● Osteoporosis: 4% Heart disease: 61% Kidney disease: 27%

+

2.5 LEGISLATION GOVERNING THE USE OF IODIZED SALT AND SALTED FOODS

The low usage of iodized salt was found to be due to lack of awareness of legislation, control and quality monitoring schemes, and enforcement of existing regulation on the production, distribution, sale and usage of iodized salt (Kissi, 2012). Legislation requiring the mandatory iodization of salt was passed by several Sub-Sahara African States which even extends to the usage of salt in households (Kissi, 2012). Wheeler and Van der Haar, (2004) had stated that in 1994, the Benin Government enacted legislation requiring that all edible salt including that intended for animal consumption be iodized. This legislation mandated all salt to have iodine of 20-40ppm KIO₃. Egyptian government in 1996 had similarly enacted salt legislation requiring the iodization of table salt with 50-80 ppm KIO₃ (Wheeler and Van der Haar, 2004).

The Universal Salt Iodization (USI) was initiated in Ghana in 1995 (Agle and Armah, 1999). Quality control schemes had been set by The Food and Drugs Board (Amended Act in 1996), the Ghana Standard Board, and the Ministry of Health to ensure that all salt produced locally or imported are iodized with the aim of enhancing and improving consumption at the household level and an example was the 90% household consumption target set by MOH (Dalmiya et al., 2004). The Ghana Standards Board had also mandated that the iodine content in salt should not be less than 50 ppm at the production point and at the retail level, it is expected to be at 25ppm (Food and Drugs Board Act, 1992). Buxton and Baguune 2012 had reported that The Food and Drug Board Amendment Act, 523 of 1996 on universal iodization was established to improve the usage of iodine to prevent IDD. The law requires that “No person shall mine salt for human or animal consumption, or import,

manufacture, package, label, advertise, store, deliver, distribute, trade, sell, or export any salt that is not fortified with potassium iodide (KI), or potassium iodate (KIO₃) in accordance with this Act” (Food and Drugs Board Act, 1992).

2.6 FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH CONSUMPTION OF IODIZED SALT AND SALTED FOODS

2.6.1 Coverage Level

Available data in 1999 about the effort to control IDD indicated that African countries had achieved varying degrees of progress based on coverage data from rapid assessment using test kits to test salt in households. The coverages of 90%, 23% and 71% has been achieved by Republic of Benin, Burkina Faso and Togo respectively (Agble and Armah, 1999). The Ghana Demographic and Health Survey (GDHS) of 1998 had reported a national coverage of 16 percent. Nation-wide assessment by Agble and Armah, 1999 also had reported the national coverage in Ghana as 22.1 percent. Coverage level of 8.1% from the results of a quick assessment of coverage in 1998 in the Kintampo district had also been reported (Kintampo District, 1998). Global goal of eliminating IDD seemed blur for Ghana.

2.6.2 Demographic and Socio-Economic Factors

The assessment study by Agble and Armah, 1999 noted that IDD and iodized salt knowledge difference difference between male and female respondents was very narrow but urban residents tended to consume more iodized salt than those in the rural areas.

2.6.3 Level of Knowledge

Educating the general public on IDD and the benefits of iodized salt, minimizes misconceptions about IDD, and to promote behaviour change in order to raise iodine status in the population has been the objective of the education programme. Even after attaining sufficient levels of iodised salt consumption, education must continue (Salt Institute, 2002). Recent nutrition surveys in the USA show small but steady erosion in American iodine intake and it has been addressed by stepping up continuous education (Salt Institute, 2002). A KABP study in Ghana had reported that the cause of goitre was not known by 66 % of the respondents (Asibey et al., 1995). Agble and Armah, 1999 had report on lack of information, poor attitude towards acceptance of iodised salt and misconceptions about iodized salt were cited as important obstacles on the use of iodized salt especially in Ghana. The fact that people have knowledge about iodized salt does not always mean that they will use it. It has been shown that consumption depends on availability as well as cost.

2.6.4 Availability

In the assessment study conducted in Ghana (Agble and Armah, 1999) found positive correlation with consumption of iodized salt which is the major reason for use of uniodized salt and 52.3% respondent had complain of unavailability. The cost of iodisation is known to be extremely low that is only about US\$0.05 per person per year (WHO, 2001), compared to packaging and transportation. In the US, salt producers co-operated with public health authorities and made the cost of both iodised and plain salt to consumers the same whereas the availability of cheaper non-iodised salt is perhaps the most persistent problem for IDD Control programmes in developing countries, including Ghana, demands effective and durable solutions. Iodized salt has been considered expensive was another reason for it non-use (Agble

and Armah, 1999; Venkatesh et al., 1995). However, there was an approval by The Food and Drugs Board for bulk packaging of 25- and 50-kilogram weight of iodized salt in 1998 to enable traders' re-bag into quantities which consumers can afford (Agble and Armah, 1999).

2.6.5 Aesthetic Characteristics

Characteristics such as size of granules, colour and taste affect the choice of salt and therefore cannot be overlooked. Four types of salt were identified, namely coarse, granular, fine and rock salt in the coverage assessment by MOH in 1999. The order of usage was coarse salt, granular followed by fine and salt. The reason for the choices is that people are familiar to the unrefined characteristics (size of granules, colour, and taste) of non-iodized salt. There is a belief also that iodized salt "spoils soups". This is probably because iodized salt is refined and concentrated. Education attempts have not been very effective could be reason for the persistence of such beliefs. Ranganathan, 1999 found that iodine is lost by 20% after 12 months when coarse salt was iodized with iodide at normal room temperature and moderate humidity. (Salt Institute, 2002).

CHAPTER THREE

METHOD

3.0 Study Design

The study was conducted in the halls of University of Cape Coast, one of the public universities in Ghana using cross-sectional design. UCC is a host of many students originating from all the ten geographical regions and enumeration areas (EA) of Ghana therefore UCC halls could serve as a direct random representative of Ghana population.

3.1 Study Population and Sampling Procedure

The study population comprised all students aged 15 years and above residing in the halls of University of Cape Coast who cook with salt. Three hundred participants, 150 each of males and females were randomly selected for the study between old and new site hall residences of University of Coast. The sampling procedure involved the assignment of structured questionnaires which was accepted by the supervisor to all students of the six traditional halls on UCC campus. Prior to the administration of the questionnaires, the questionnaires were pre-tested in non-selected area. The necessary modifications, challenges and corrections were addressed before it will be finally administered in the study area. Descriptive and inferential statistical analysis was conducted.

3.2 Research Instrument

A questionnaire was used to assess the knowledge of the benefits of iodized salt and - knowledge about consumption of salted foods in general with the questions ‘What benefit(s) of iodized salt consumption do you know?’ and ‘Do you know a recommended amount of salt to be eaten per person per day?’. Knowledge on consumption of salted foods among students was obtained from the questionnaire

where respondents were asked what health problems are caused by high salt diet to assess their knowledge about the risk of salted foods.

3.3 Data Analysis

SPSS version 22 was used to analyse the data. Frequency and percentages of the data describing the demographic characteristic of respondents was computed using descriptive univariate analysis. The relationships and associations between variables were analyzed using Pearson Chi-Square test. This test was used to establish the association of the knowledge of iodized salt and salted food usage with demographic characteristics.

3.4 Ethical Consideration

Informed consent was obtained from all the students before the questionnaire was given out.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULT

TABLE 4.0: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

DEMOGRAPHICS	CHARACTERISTICS	N (%)
Sex	Male	177 (59.0)
	Female	122 (40.7)
Age	<20	38 (12.7)
	20-29	225 (75.0)
	30-39	8 (2.7)
	>39	1 (0.3)
Marital Status	Single	274 (91.3)
	Married	15 (5.0)
	Divorced	0 (0)
	Living with partner	9 (3.0)
	Windowed	0 (0)
Level of Education	100	116 (38.7)
	200	50 (16.7)
	300	70 (23.3)
	400	57 (19.0)
	Master/PhD	4 (1.3)
	Program of Study	Biological science
Physical science		25 (8.3)
Medical science		19 (6.3)
Arts		17 (5.7)
Social science		31 (10.3)
Business		35 (11.7)
Education		50 (16.7)
Hall		Nkrumah
	Valco	49 (16.7)
	Casford	50 (16.7)
	Adehye	34 (11.3)
	Atlantic	43 (14.3)
	Oguaa	53 (17.7)
Ethnicity	Akan	201 (67)
	Ewe	29 (9.7)
	Mole-dagbane	9 (3.0)
	Guan	4 (1.3)
	Ga-adangbe	24 (8.0)
	Other	26 (8.7)

Male respondents recruited for the study were three fifth (59%) and female respondents were two fifth (41%). Age group 20-29 years recorded about three quarter followed closely by <20 age group with little more than one-tenth (13%). Nearly all the students (91%) showed single as marital status meanwhile about two fifth (39%) were first year student and the rest scattered within second and third year. About one fifth (19%) were fourth years while just 1% of respondents were Master/PhD students. Programme of study showed highest for Education programmes close to one fifth (17%) followed by Business, with Art programmes as the lowest (6%) respondents. Among the traditional hall in UCC, Kwame Nkrumah Hall led with one fifth (20%) respondent trailed by Ogua Hall with just a little below one fifth (18%). Majority (67%) of the respondents were of the Akan tribe while Ewe were only one tenth (10%) of the respondent and very few (1%) were Guans.

Table 4.1: Respondents Knowledge and Awareness of Iodized Salt

Knowledge and Awareness of Iodized Salt	Percent %
Have You Heard About Iodized Salt?	
Yes	293 (97.7)
No	7 (2.3)
Type of Salt Used	
Iodized Salt	280 (93.30)
Non-Iodized Salt	20 (6.70)
How to Differentiate Between Salt Types	
Texture	28 (15.20)
Logo	32 (17.40)
Refined Iodine	93 (50.50)
Size	25 (13.60)
Taste	6 (3.30)
Source of Information about Iodized Salt	
Television	209 (48.30)
Radio	82 (18.90)
Health Worker	31 (7.20)
Relative Friend	27 (6.20)
Mobile Van	11 (2.50)
Salt Seller	32 (7.40)
Newspaper Magazine	12 (2.80)
Others	29 (6.70)
Benefits of Consumption of Iodized Salt	
Know	215 (71.6)
Prevent Goitre	140 (65.10)
Improves Brain Functions	15 (7.00)
Prevent Iodine Deficiency Disorder	11 (5.10)
Provide Iodine	36 (16.70)
Thyroid Function	13 (6.10)
Don't Know	85 (28.3)
What Factors Affect Your Access to Iodized Salt	
Cost	70 (23.30)
Availability	78 (26.00)
Brand Types	127 (42.30)
Accessibility	25 (8.30)
Do you know any policy and law on production, Selling and usage of iodized salt in Ghana?	
Yes	9 (3)
No	279 (93)
Missing	12 (4)

Almost all Respondents (98%) had heard about iodized salt while the proportion use of iodized salt were 93%. About half of respondents (51%) had reported that they could only differentiate between iodized salt and non-iodized salt by the fact that iodized salt is refined with iodine included but only few respondents (3%) could differentiate between the salts by tasting it. The respondents' knowledge about the benefits of iodized salt gave rise to many possible benefits of which just little above three fifth (65%) knew it prevent Goitre and 6% knew it helps in thyroid functions meanwhile 93% had no idea about Policy and law on production, selling, and usage of iodized salt in Ghana. About half (48%) of the respondents had reported that their main source of information about iodized salt were Television seconded by radio occupying nearly one fifth (19%) of respondents as the source of information. About 42% of respondents had said that the brand types of iodized salt affected their access to iodized salt than one-quarter respondents (26%) saying the availability and the cost (23%) of iodized salt followed by 8% accessibility affected their access to iodized salt.

Table 4.2 Respondents' Sources of salt and Knowledge about High Salt Intake

RESPONDENTS KNOWLEDGE ABOUT SALT INTAKE	N (%)
Use Salt In Cooking	
Yes	291 (97)
No	3 (1)
Missing	6 (2)
Salted Fish	
Yes	274 (91.3)
No	20 (6.7)
Missing	6 (2)
Salted Beef	
Yes	237 (79)
No	56 (18.7)
Missing	7 (2.3)
Add Salt At Table	
Yes	75 (25)
No	208 (69.3)
Missing	17 (5.7)
Use Salty Ingredients	
Yes	242 (80.7)
No	44 (14.7)
Missing	14 (4.7)
Know Recommended Daily Intake Salt	
Yes	19 (6.3)
No	265 (88.3)
Missing	16 (5.3)
Making Effort In Reducing Salt Intake	
Yes	186 (62)
No	75 (25)
Missing	39 (13)
High Salt Problems	
Know	126 (42.0)
Hypertension	73 (57.90)
Hypernatrimia	3 (2.40)
Stroke	8 (6.30)
Cardiovascular Diseases	9 (7.10)
Diabetes	7 (5.60)
Kidney Problems	9 (7.10)
Goitre	17 (13.50)
Don't Know	174 (58.0)

Nearly hundred percent (97%) of respondent had reported that they use salt during meal preparations emphasizing that different sources of salt diets and ingredients were used during meal preparation. Salted fish like 'kobi' and 'Momone' were used by 91% respondents while little above three-quarters (79%) respondents used salted beef/pork, about one-fifth (19%) had not been using salted beef/pork. The habit of adding salt to already prepared food at the table were seen in only 25% of the people but 69% respondents were against that habit. Also, salty ingredients/spices usage were observed in above three-quarters (81%) of respondents meanwhile 88% respondents had reported that they don't know anything about the recommended daily intake of salt and salt ingredient/spices hence they take salt as much as they needed it with only 6% who knew it. The respondents were then asked if they knew about the health problems of high salt intake of which more than half (58%) knew it causes hypertension followed by about one-tenth (15%) who knew it could cause stroke and kidney problems. However, about 62% respondents had been making an effort to reduce salt intake either by no salt intake or using little salt when cooking while one quarter (25%) had not been making effort in reducing salt-intake.

Table 4.3 Chi-Square Association between Demographic Characteristics, and Awareness of Iodized Salt and Salt Usage

Demographic Characteristics	Ever Heard of Iodized salt		Use Salt in Your Cooking	
	Chi-square	P value	Chi-square	P value
Sex	0.444	0.505	0.067	0.796
Age Group	4.835	0.184	0.421	0.936
Marital status	1.466	0.481	0.271	0.873
Level of education	11.542	0.021	4.916	0.296
Program of study	6.294	0.391	5.491	0.483
Hall	5.44	0.365	6.399	0.269
Ethnicity	7.215	0.205	5.211	0.391

From this table, an association of demographics with knowledge about iodized salt and salt usage was tested with Pearson’s Chi-Square of independents. Knowledge of iodized salt was not dependent on sex, age group, marital status, program of study, hall of residence and ethnicity of respondents ($p > 0.05$). Educational level of respondents was highly associated with knowledge of iodized salt ($X^2 = 11.54$, $p = 0.021$), implying that a respondent’s knowledge about iodized salt was dependent on his/her educational background.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 DISCUSSION

This study adds up and also is contrary to some of the loads of evidence emanating mostly from previous studies. We found proportion use of iodized salt to be about 93% of respondent which is a quite appreciable increase than the findings from previous studies that had recorded a national prevalence of 22.1 percent (Agble and Armah, 1999). This increase in iodized salt among UCC student could be due to the fact that these students were literate adult who knew that iodized salt could help memory functions thus studying. Another study conducted at kintampo District 1998 had revealed only 8.1% of respondents used iodized salt while GSS, 2015 had recorded that more than three quarters of women age 15-49 have heard about iodized salt. Among iodized salt users, the study revealed that knowledge that iodized salt prevent goitre (about 65% respondents) was one of the key reasons given for the use of iodized salt. This finding is quite similar and in agreement with Adjei, 2002 who reported that knowledge on goitre was one of the key determinants in the use of iodized salt. The more people become knowledgeable about the benefits of iodized salt, the more likely they will use it yet awareness on iodized salt alone may not be enough to encourage it usage.

Availability was not a great factor with respect to this study in terms of general accessibility of iodized salt yet it accounted for one quarter of respondents. This was contrary to a survey by Buxton and Baguune, (2012) conducted in the Bia District in the Western Region in Ghana which reported unavailability of iodized salt as a principal reason for non-use of iodized salt. A little below one-quarter of the respondents indicated that, iodized salt was relatively expensive than the local salt. This point of this study piles up to the findings of Yamada et al., 1998; Ghana Health

Service, 2003; Buxton and Baguune, 2012; UNICEF, 2008 which all the above studies had indicated that price was a significant factor to the use of iodized salt. Two unresolved issues may account for the influence of availability and affordability. Firstly, the fact that small-scale producers flood the markets with cheaper un-iodized salt. Secondly production and packaging of iodized salt at affordable cost.

About half (48%) of the respondents had reported that their main source of information about iodized salt was through Television. Mass media cannot be denied for their effort in disseminating information as well as salt traders also being important channel for source of information on iodized salt especially in rural areas. Amoussou-Gohoungbo in his study in 2000, found that as much as 70 percent of salt traders in the Hohoe District had low level of awareness on iodized salt. The study revealed that almost all (93%) of the respondents never knew of the existence of policy regulating iodized salt intake. This could be a key contributor to the failure of the national target of ensuring a 90% Ghanaian consumption of iodized salt set by Minister of Health (Agble and Armah, 1999). This contradicts with the Food and Drugs Board Act of (1992). The policy states that “No person shall mine salt for human or animal consumption, or import, manufacture, package, label, advertise, store, deliver, distribute, trade, sell, or export any salt that is not fortified with potassium iodide (KI), or potassium iodate (KIO₃) in accordance with this Act” (Agble and Armah, 1999).

Majority (97%) of the respondents in this study reported that salt had been an inevitable ingredient in their meal preparation. GSS, 2015 had reported that about half (46%) of the Ghana population consume salts from different sources. Among the many sources of salt, the study has shown that more than three-quarters consume salt

from salty ingredient like Maggie cube followed by dried salty fish like 'kobi'. This observing was quite opposite to the findings of GSS, 2015 which had revealed that Ghanaians consume salt more from processed foods than bouillon cubes. Charlton et al., 2010 had confirmed that about 88% respondents of a survey had identified processed foods such as bread, tinned food and takeaway as the main source of salt in diet. This difference in this study was because the study respondents were students who were able to read food labels allowing them to avoid salted processed food. About the knowledge on recommended daily intake of salt, only 6% of the respondents knew. Findings from Grimes et al., 2009; Charlton et al., 2010 and Claro et al., 2012, had recorded similar result. In this study, Knowledge on diet-diseases relationship regarding salt intake were seen in a little less than half (42%) of respondents while the rest never knew about this diet-diseases relationship. More than half of the respondents who knew about diet-disease relationship knew that hypertension was the main health problem following high salt intake. These findings pile up to Wyllie et al., 2011; Kim et al., 2012 and Zhang et al., 2013 which had also recorded hypertension as highly related to high salt intake.

5.1 CONCLUSION

Knowledge of the benefits of iodized salt was very high among students. Knowledge about iodized salt among the students was dependent on their educational level hence there was association. Also, the students did not know about policy regulating the production and selling of iodized salt. Dried salted fish was mostly consumed by the students but majority of the students were unaware of the health problems associated with high salt intake.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

- Education on causes of goitre and benefits of iodized salt should be intensified among salt traders and persons responsible for making decisions at home as far as meal preparations are concerned.
- Appropriate channel through the mass media for reaching rural communities with information on iodized salt should be considered.
- The government should use social marketing techniques to promote iodized salt at cheaper prices to make iodized salt financially accessible.
- Salt used by restaurant, canteens and on markets should be sampled for analysis at the Food Science Laboratories to ensure that all salt contains the recommended amount of iodine.

APPENDIX

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RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE

PARTICIPANT DEMOGRAPHICS

1.Age	AGE	
	AGE_G	<20.....1 20-29....2 30-39....3 >30.....4
2.Sex	SEX	Male ()1 Female ().....2
3. Marital status	MARI_STAT	Single ().....1 married ()2 divorced ().....3 living with a partner ().....4 Widowed ().....5
4. level	LEVEL	100 ()1 200 ().....2 300 ().....3 400 ()4 Masters/PhD ().....5
5. Program	PROG	BIOLOGICAL SCIENCE.....1 PHYSICAL SCIENCE.....2 MEDICAL SCIENCE.....3 ARTS.....4 SOCIAL SCIENCE.....5 BUSINESS6 EDUCATION.....7
6. Hall of residence	HALL_RES	Nkrumah ()1 Valco ().....2 Casford ()3 Adehye ()4 Atlantic ().....5 Oguaa ()6
7. Ethnicity	ETHNICITY	Akan ().....1 Ewe ().....2 Mole-Dagbane ().....3 Guan ().....4 Ga-Adangbe ().....5 Other (Specify)6

SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS

8a.Are you in any income generating activity/employment?	INC_GEN_BUS	Yes ().....1 No ().....2
8b. If Yes, in 8(a) indicate the activity/business	INDIC_BUS	TRADER.....1 TEACHER....2 COMPANY WORKER....3 NO BUSINES.....4
9. How much income do you earn in a month?	INC_EARN	

KNOWLEDGE ABOUT IODIZED SALT AND IDD

9a. Have you heard about Iodized Salt?	HEARD_IOD_SALT	Yes ()..... 1 No ()..... 2
9b. If Yes what was your main source of information?	IOD_SOUR_INF O_1	Television ().. 1 Radio ().. 2 Health worker ().. 3 Relative/friend ().. 4 Mobile van ().. 5 Salt sellers ().... 6 Newspaper/Magazine ().. 7 Other (Specify) 8
10a. What type of salt do you use in cooking?	SALT_TYP_USE	Iodized salt ().. 1 Non-iodized salt () .. 2
10b. if you use iodized salt, any reason?	IOD_SALT_RS ON	IODINE CONTENT....1 MEDICATED....2 GOITRE PREVENTION...3 MOST AVAILABILITY....4 BLANK.....5
10c. If you use non-iodized salt, any reason?	NON-IOD_RSON	
11a. Can you differentiate iodized salt from non-iodized salt?	DIFF_IOD_NONI OD	Yes ()..... 1 No ()..... 2
11b If yes how can you differentiate iodized salt from non-iodized salt?	HOW_TO_DIFF	TEXTURE...1 SIZE...2 LOGO.....3 REFINED...4 SOLUBILITY....5 BLANK.....6
12. What benefit(s) of iodized salt consumption do you know?	IOD_SALT_BEN EFIT	PREVENT GOITRE.....1 IMPROVE BRAIN FUNCTIONS....2 PREVENT IDD.....3 BLANK.....4
13a. Do you know any iodine deficiency disorders?	KNOW_IDD	Yes ()..... 1 No ()..... 2
13b. If Yes, Mention them?	MENT_IDD	GOITRE...1 MENTAL RETARDATION.....2 CRETINISM.....3 BLANK.....4
14. What health condition(s) can iodized salt prevent?	HEALTH_IOD_PR EVT	GOITRE...1 MENTAL RETARDATION.....2 CRETINISM.....3 BLANK.....4

AVAILABILITY, COST AND ACCESSIBILITY

15. Do you always get Iodized Salt to buy?	IOD_BUY	Yes () 1 No ()..... 2
16. Where do you normally buy iodized salt from?	WHERE_IOD_BUY	Market ()..... 1 Petty trader ()..... 2 Street vendor/Hawkers ().... 3 Supermarket ().. 4
17. What factor(s) affects your access to iodized salt?	FACTORS_AFF_IOD	Cost ()..... 1 Availability ()..... 2 Brand types ()..... 3 Accessibility ()..... 4

18a. Do the costs of iodized salt affect your choice of salt intake?	COST_AFF_IOD	Yes ()..... 1 No ()..... 2
18b. If yes any reason?	COST_AFFIODRSO	HIGH PRICE...1 LOW PRICE...2

AWARENESS OF LEGISLATURE

19a. Do you know any policy and law on production, selling, and usage of iodized salt in Ghana?	IOD_POLICY	Yes ()..... 1 No ()... 2
19b. If Yes, what is this policy or law?	WHAT_POLICY	
20. What can you say to encourage people to use iodized salt?	ENCORGE_IOD_USE	

KNOWLEDGE AND CONSUMPTION OF SALTY FOODS

21a. Do you use salt in your cooking?	SALT_COOKIN	Yes ()..... 1 No ()..... 2
21b. If Yes, how often do you use salt in cooking?	OFT_SALT_COOK	All meals cooked ()..... 1 Some meals cooked ()..... 2
22a. Do you eat salted fish (Koobe/ momone)	EAT_SALT_FISH	Yes ()..... 1 No ()..... 2
22b. If Yes, How often?	OFT_SALT_FISH	In all prepared stews/soups ()... 1 In some prepared stews/soups ().. 2
23a. Do you eat salted beef/ pork?	EAT_SALT_BEEF	Yes ()..... 1 No ()..... 2
23b. If Yes How often?	OFT_SALT_BEEF	In all prepared stews/soups () 1 In some prepared stews/soups ()... 2
24a. Do you add salt at the table?	ADD_SALT_TABLE	Yes ()..... 1 No ()..... 2
24b. If Yes, how often do you add salt to food at the table?	OFT_SALT_TABLE	At all times ()..... 1 Sometimes ()..... 2
25a. Do you use salty ingredient like Maggie cube and others for cooking?	USE_SALT_INGRE_COOK	Yes ()..... 1 No ()..... 2
25b. If Yes, how often?	OFT_USE_SALT_IN GRE	In all prepared stews/soups ()..... 1 In some prepared stews/soups ().... 2

26a. Do you know a recommended amount of salt to be eaten per day?	KNOW_RECOM_SALT	Yes ().....1 No ().....2
26b. If Yes can you indicate the amount?	INDIC_AMNT	
27. Do you pay attention to package labels?	ATTEN_PAC_LAB	Yes ().....1 No ().....2
28. Do you like the labelling of salt indications on foods?	LIKE_SALT_INDIC	Yes ().....1 No ().....2
28b. If Yes, any reason?	LIKE_SALT_INDIC_RSON	INSTRUCTIONS....1 CAUTION....2 SALT/INGRE CONTENT....3 BLANK.....4
29. What is the source of your knowledge or information about salt?	SOURC_INFO_SALT 2	Television ().....1 Radio ()...2 Health worker ()...3 Relative/friend ()....4 Salt sellers ().....5 Internet ().....6 Newspaper/Magazine ().....7 Other (Specify).....8

RISK OF SALTY FOODS CONSUMPTION

30. What health problems are caused by high salt diet?	PROB_HIGH_SALT	HYPERTENSION...1 HYPERNATRIMIA...2 STROKE....3 CVD.....4 DON'T KNOW...5
31a. Do you suffer from any of this health problem?	SUFF_HELTH_PROB	Yes ()1 No ().....2
31b. If yes, what health problem?	WHT_HELTH_PROB	HYPERTENSION...1 HYPERNATRIMIA...2 STROKE....3 CVD.....4 DON'T KNOW...5
32. Do you think that salt reduction or limitation could help improve your health?	SALT_REDTN_IPRV_HELTH	Yes ().....1 No ().....2
34a. Are you making an effort to reduce your salt intake?	EFF_REDTN_SALT_INTAKE	Yes ().....1 No ().....2
34b. If yes, what efforts?	WHT_EFF_REDTN_SALT	NO SALT INTAKE....1 SALT REDUCTION...2 NO EFFORT....3
34c. If No, why?	NO_EFF_SALT_REDTN	